

DESIGN OF INTERACTIONS FOR SOCIAL APPROPRIATION OF KNOWLEDGE

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a case study of Parque Explora's most recent museographic renovation project, which reflects the intentions of a team that aimed to stimulate visitors' appropriation of tools for the creation of contents, resulting in the interactive exhibit *On Stage: Stories behind Stories (En Escena: Historias tras las historias)*, launched at the end of 2013. It demonstrates how, through the area of design, it is possible to contribute to the development of scientific ability, public appropriation of knowledge and the building of citizenship, reinforcing both the Parque Explora as an interactive museum and its role as a "Knowledge Broker" within the ecosystem of innovation in the city of Medellín.

KEY WORDS: *Museography, design, social appropriation, education, innovation*

INTRODUCTION

Starting in 1960, science museums began to radically change their approach, placing special emphasis on providing visitors with a direct experience with physical, natural and technical phenomena. This was done under the assumption that it would allow these visitors to strengthen their confidence and capacity to understand the world around them. (Allen, 2004)

The era's interest in transforming the education system proposed interactivity as an answer to the necessity of learning based on experience and not solely on content. Artifacts were designed (Franco-Avellaneda, 2013) with the aim of presenting and permitting the interaction of visitors with certain phenomena through *interactive* exhibits. Since then, museographers have found themselves facing a series of challenges when creating some of these spaces: with the visitor in mind, the exhibits should facilitate his learning, support him in decision-making (where to go, what to do, and how to understand his interactions) and motivate him at each step of the interaction. This challenge also requires that the design process be supported, from an early stage, by a strong research and evaluation program. (Allen & Gutwill, 2004)

In a similar manner the Parque Explora, an interactive museum in the city of Medellín, has understood and taken on these challenges in the development of its exhibits, through a design process that is based on a work paradigm (Jaramillo, 2011) where the horizontal dialogue between the *what* and the *how* are maintained throughout each project, searching

for equilibrium between contents and stimuli through conversations between museologists, museographicists, scientists, researchers, and the public.

THE RENOVATION

As a science museum located in the city of Medellín, the Parque Explora is a space dedicated to creating stimuli for the visitor. It aims to encourage the public appropriation of knowledge, the development of scientific ability, and the building of citizenship through a renewed offer of permanent and temporary exhibits for its public.

ON STAGE: *Stories behind Stories* is an interactive space, with 900 square meters distributed over two floors, where visitors experiment with different means of expression (communication). Through the use of close to 35 analogue, digital, individual and collective experiences, the visitor produces content under the premise of learning by doing: as he experiments, the visitor gains awareness and appropriates knowledge. (Aguirre et. al., 2013)

More than understanding the way the communication devices and technologies work, the room aims to provide an immersive and personalized experience. It is an exhibit created for a diverse public, as one of the premises in the design was not to base itself on previously held knowledge of its visitors, but on the emotions derived from their interactions with the phenomena, objects, metaphors, and scenographies. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Panoramic photo of the exhibition.

A MACHINE THAT CREATES WORLDS

The place that contains an exhibit, unlike any other spaces, is characterized by being a complement to a series of objects, both as a container and as a transmitting vehicle. The space is an essential element, which recreates three dimensionally, the coexistence between object, place, atmosphere and meaning. (Perez, 2007).

This new exhibit is not a space dedicated to information and communication technologies (ITC), but a space to be used for expression and creation, where stories take precedence over technique. The museographic design, then, is meant to use discussion and the different graphic, object and spatial languages to stimulate creativity, expressivity, and individual and collective experimentation.

Conceptually, the exhibit is viewed as a stage, where the visitor is creator, actor and audience; the theater is viewed as a physical configuration, where the stage comes to life due to the sum of events, actions and effects that are produced through the spaces and mechanisms that are found around the stage. The interactive room, seen as a whole, is a great machine that creates worlds, that creates stories. (Figure 2)

The interior space is revealed through beams of warm light, the metallic support structures blend with the shadows to reveal the wood, the objects, the titles, and the scenes, all blended together in virtual spaces, visible spaces, that do not intimidate but instead invite. The visitor traverses the space freely, following his own interests, finding out and creating his own interpretations.

Figure 2. Images of the concept of the interactive room.

Figure 3. Visualization of the space. Conceptual approximation.

In each scene, the objects are converted into tools. The space is a workshop, a place for creation and co-creation, from experimentation with camera effects to shadow play and anything between and including rotoscoping, acoustics, video games, discourses, and content for social networks, etc. (Figure 3)

Thus an exhibition is proposed where multiple situations are simultaneously rolled out in each of the spaces through interactive experiences. With a theatrical conceptual base, the experiences are grouped into four zones: Effects, Representation, Discourse and Behind the Scenes. Each one of these interactive experiences is selected because it presents the same possibilities of museographic and museologic dialogue, always keeping in mind the essential criterion of interactivity.

INTERACTIVE SCENES

Interactivity signifies dialogue (Wagensberg, 2001); it is the reciprocity of action, where the visitor acts and the exhibit responds in some way (Allen et al., 2004). This dialogue is physical-emotional and it manifests itself in the interrelation between form, function, and technology experienced over time (Kolko, 2011).

Through horizontal dialogues between content and form, the design team looks to create attractive, functional, useful pieces and at the same time generate compelling and motivating interactions. Going farther than third dimensionality, the team also designs in a fourth dimension: time.

The time considerations allow the designers, from early on in the process, to imagine how the visitor will approach the artifacts: how his attention will be attracted, how he understands their functioning, what kind of actions must be carried out, and what emotions or sensations are brought out in the users and experienced in an individual and/or collective way.

During the development of the project through the use of prototypes, evaluations with a live public are vital in order to verify and redefine the interactions, making sure that the final result works as an effective vehicle and generator of stimuli towards the social appropriation of knowledge.

Based on the *total interactivity* model of Wagensberg (2000), this exhibit employs museographic elements to simultaneously generate three kinds of stimuli in the visitor: sensory stimuli, creative stimuli, and social stimuli. Thus:

- **Sensory stimuli:** The visitor is considered an active element within the exhibition. Experiences are designed to interact with the body and stimulate the senses, where pleasure is generated by the provocation of nature and the response produced.
- **Creative stimuli:** The goal is that the visitor should find common elements within diversity among spaces designed for exploration, discovery, and creation.
- **Social stimuli:** Experiences meant to promote participation and collective interaction through provocative and embracing spaces. In many cases, interactions take on meaning or are completed when they are shared with others.

All of these stimuli are intertwined in each interactive experience. A person may feel himself or herself visually attracted to a space. Once in contact with the space, the person becomes interested in understanding what it is about and presses the bright red button. He decides to experiment and is surprised by the result obtained. He reflects on what happened and tries again, finally sharing the experience with others and initiating conversations.

Below, two interactive experiences developed for this project will be presented as examples to illustrate each of the stimuli previously mentioned.

Example 2: *Minor Stories: In a Given Moment*

There is an interactive video game equipped with a tangible interface using a mapping projection technique on a relief table. An aboriginal community on an island is created, where there are plants, animals, villagers and a shaman who prays to the heavens when facing an intense summer or a harsh winter. The visitors share complete control of the situation, moving and rotating objects around the projected surface. Handling these objects, the visitors can create different situations: they may change the day into night, summer into winter, create bird and UFO effects, and even inflict natural disasters on specific regions. (See figure 4)

Figure 4. Photograph of visitor interacting with cubes to modify the virtual environment.

- **Sensory Stimuli:** The video projection on a relief surface surprises the visitor, who also finds himself with some objects that allow him to interact with the game in a new and tangible manner.
- **Creative Stimuli:** Each visitor is invited to experiment and create his/her own short story.
- **Social Stimuli:** Three people may simultaneously share the experience and observe the results.

Example 2: *Gestures: Distinguishing Marks*

An emergency situation at a nuclear power plant is reenacted to incentivize group communication through gestures and to resolve a problem. One of the participants enters a cabin that simulates an alarm situation and only this participant has ac-

Figure 5. Photograph of visitors using gestures to solve a challenge.

cess to the command control; the participants that are in front of the cabin give him instructions through gestures (through a soundproof window), in the hope that he will deactivate the alarm by following a sequence of steps. (See figure 5)

- **Sensory Stimuli:** An emergency situation at a Soviet nuclear power plant is reenacted, conserving the aesthetic and visual language, and therefore giving a tangible and realistic dimension to the experience. The sensation is made more intense and immersive with sound and light effects.
- **Creative Stimuli:** The result depends on the effectiveness, resourcefulness and histrionism of the characters.
- **Social Stimuli:** A challenge is posed through the detection of a communications system failure at the plant; it may only be resolved collectively and through non-verbal language.

STIMULI FOR APPROPRIATION

These stimuli go beyond the pleasure or fun of interacting with the exhibition; they are only worthwhile if they are able to motivate the visitor to enquire, to reach his own conclusions and interpretations, and to relate the experience with his own life. A good science museum is above all an instrument for social change. "... the principal function of a museum is that the visit changes (the visitor's) life. If (he) has more questions when (he) exits than when (he) enters, it is a good sign." (Wagensberg et. al., 2006).

CLOSING COMMENTS

This article reflects the intentions of a multidisciplinary team that designed a museography renovation project for the Parque Explora called *On Stage: Stories behind Stories* (*En Escena: Historias tras las historias*), a process that is enriched by horizontal conversations between the what and the how. These dialogues allow the team to conceive of a welcoming space that is, on the one hand, conceptually forceful and stimulating, and, on the other hand, allows for the design and development of a series of objects and interactive pieces, "scenes", that stimulate creativity, histrionics, and collective participation.

Special emphasis was placed on interactivity — the dialogue between the visitor and the exhibition. Three types of necessary stimuli were considered for the development of the interactive exhibit: social, sensory, and creative stimuli, that are only valuable if they act as motivating vehicles towards the public appropriation of knowledge, scientific ability, and the building of citizenship. This meticulous and conscientious work that took the development team almost two years to complete, has begun to bear fruit several months after being open to the public. The smiles of the visitors, their surprised faces, and their capacity to create, express and share with others, indicate growth emerging from has been sowed by the stimuli. It is now necessary to examine these positive indications through an evaluation process.

On Stage: Stories behind Stories is a great machine that creates stories from memories that extend beyond the boundaries of the museum. It is a space where design contributes to the strengthening of Parque Explora's role as a "knowledge broker" in the city's ecosystem of innovation, recently recognized internationally as the "most innovative in the world". The interpretation of "innovation" in this case is more directed towards the social construction of knowledge, by sparking in its citizens creative stimuli from the multiple stories that are created in the exhibition.

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